

Article

Sustainable Supply Chain Management and Disruptive Theory: a Bibliometric Review

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Abstract: *Sustainable Supply Chain Management stands at the forefront of contemporary business strategies. Concurrently, the emergence of Disruptive Theory has reshaped conventional notions of supply chain dynamics, introducing innovative technologies and strategies that challenge traditional practices. This study investigates the impact of disruptive technologies on Supply Chain Management within emerging economies, with a specific emphasis on the South African context. The study addresses critical gaps in the field of technological readiness, which challenge the effective integration of disruptive technologies. Using bibliometric analysis, the study evaluated the contributions of academia, industry, and government to developing disruptive theory in supply chain management in South Africa. The study found a significant increase in research activity in 2022, with 71.6% of publications focusing on disruptive theory in supply chain management. The findings highlight the need for collaboration among academia, industry, and governmental bodies to advance disruptive theory in South African supply chain management and promote sustainability. Further, it provides a foundation for further exploration and development of strategies to overcome challenges and leverage opportunities in the rapidly evolving supply chain management landscape. Future researchers may explore a deductive research approach to understand how disruptive theory applies explicitly to the unique challenges and dynamics of the South African supply chain.*

Keywords: *Sustainable Supply Chain; Disruptive theory; Disruptive Innovation; Disruptive Technology.*

1. Introduction

Disruptive technologies, such as autonomous vehicles and drones, have significantly impacted last-mile delivery in South Africa, improving delivery routes, reducing delivery times, and improving customer experience (Yu, Hang, 2010). E-commerce has also impacted supply chain management practices, requiring adaptive approaches to inventory management, fulfilment, and logistics (Khan, Arif, 2023). Disruptive technologies have enabled seamless order processing, warehouse automation, and efficient distribution, allowing businesses to stay competitive in the digital marketplace (Martínez-Vergara, Valls-Pasola, 2019). They also influence sustainability and environmental responsibility, enabling organisations to monitor and reduce their carbon footprint, implement green practices, and embrace sustainable sourcing and manufacturing processes (Khan, 2022).

South Africa, an emerging economy, faces unique challenges in supply chain management and disruptive theory. However, there needs to be a more comprehensive understanding of the evolution, trends, and impact of research in these areas (Bayode et al., 2019). This knowledge gap hinders informed decision-making, strategy development, and innovation in the field (Peters et al., 2001). A bibliometric study is needed to systematically assess existing research, identify key trends, address challenges faced by researchers, policymakers, and industry practitioners in the absence of systematic analysis and seek to identify key themes relevant to South Africa (Gencer, Akkucuk, 2020).

The study aims to provide the current research trajectory, identifying gaps and highlighting influential contributors (Chapman, 2021). The findings will guide academics, practitioners, and policymakers in making informed decisions, formulating effective strategies, and driving innovation in supply chain management. The study will seek to answer whether there are any emerging or underexplored areas within disruptive theory and supply chain management (SCM) research that South African scholars could investigate further (Ikram et al., 2018). In doing so, this study will provide a comprehensive overview of current knowledge and offer insights for further research and development, contributing to sustainable growth and competitiveness in South African industries (Queiroz et al., 2021).

The research objectives include identifying gaps, constraints, and unexplored opportunities in the existing literature, with a specific focus on areas that have received limited attention from South African scholars, as well as providing a valuable resource for South African academics, policymakers, and industry stakeholders by synthesising existing knowledge and highlighting potential avenues for further exploration and development (Nyagadza et al., 2022). This study aspires to make a meaningful contribution towards fostering sustainable growth and enhancing the competitive edge of South African industries. This study aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by focusing on SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure (Chauhan et al., 2022). It promotes resilient infrastructure, inclusive industrialisation, and an innovation-friendly environment.

Disruptive theory and supply chain management research findings can contribute to SDG 9 (Sætra, 2021). Given that disruptive theory and supply chain management research often intersect with themes of innovation and industrial practices, the findings from this study possess the potential to make a substantive contribution to the realisation of SDG 9 (Kota et al., 2021). The study also aligns with SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals, emphasising the importance of collaboration between businesses, government entities, and civil society in South Africa. These partnerships are crucial for achieving all SDGs and advancing sustainable development in the nation (Sampedro, 2021).

2. Literature review

Disruptive theory, developed on Clayton Christensen's 1997 disruptive innovation theory, aims to understand better and handle the influence of new technologies and innovations on supply chain management (Agarwal et al., 2020). Disruptive theory, also known as disruptive innovation theory, is a theory that describes how new technology, products, or services can disrupt established markets and sectors by generating new markets or fundamentally changing the way things are done (Yu, Hang, 2010). According to the notion, disruptive innovations generally begin as simple, low-cost alternatives to current products or services. Still, they improve quality and performance with time, eventually overtaking the established products or services. Clayton Christensen, who first presented the notion in his book "The Innovator's Dilemma," is frequently connected with disruptive theory (Shaw, Chisholm, 2020).

Innovation is known to positively affect developing countries and their economies, resulting in a sustainable competitive advantage for such countries and their economies that embrace these innovations (Nagano et al., 2014). South Africa, a developing nation with a sophisticated economy, is well placed to accept and absorb emerging technology, being a country with more technology reach and more than half (59%) of its population having internet access compared to the other countries in the SADC region, (Nyagadza et al., 2022).

The disruptive theory has gained significant interest in supply chain management in South Africa, as businesses face various challenges in their supply chain ecosystem. To address supply chain disruptions, businesses employ strategies like supply chain mapping, flexible transportation arrangements, and

stringent supplier selection criteria (Agigi et al., 2016). However, there needs to be more research on its social effects on communities and ecosystems (Chapman, 2021). The literature highlights the importance of start-ups in the supply chain ecosystem, their multifaceted functions, and the need for supportive mechanisms, (Nguyen Duc et al., 2019) It also discusses the transformative potential of blockchain technology in enhancing supply chain viability through increased transparency, traceability, and security while addressing implementation challenges and exploring blockchain's capability to combat product counterfeiting in supply chains, emphasising its potential to ensure product traceability and authentication (Brandín, Abrishami, 2021).

The literature also speaks to the harnessing of Additive Manufacturing (AM) for high-volume production, revealing that unconventional operations management and technological innovation can defy standard AM perceptions, achieving economies of scale and offering insights for supply chain advancements in the context of disruptive technologies, (Brandín, Abrishami, 2021) in other schools of thought, the literature aggregates studies on supply chain resilience, emphasising the importance of holistic disruption management, integrating data analytics, blockchain, AI, and strategies for disruption readiness, (Rejeb, Rejeb, 2020) The study examines blockchain technology's adoption in the Brazilian Operations and Supply Chain Management (OSCM) using a Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) -based model, finding that factors like facilitating conditions, trust, and social influence largely determine its acceptance (Jiang, Chen, 2021).

Some papers review literature using the Environmental, Technological, Legal, Cultural, and Logistical (ETLCL) framework on blockchain's role in sustainable supply chain management, underscoring its capability to boost transparency, traceability, and accountability (Queiroz et al., 2021). It also examines disruptive technologies in healthcare, focusing on novel therapies and supply chain innovations, emphasising the need for further study into measuring collaboration and trust for innovation in reverse logistics (Agarwal et al., 2020). Another publication investigates blockchain's potential to disrupt supply chain management in Indian Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) using socio-technical factors and sustainability. Lastly, the research examines the integration of organisational theory into business intelligence and big data, categorising 33 theories based on their impact and suggesting a future focus on Business Intelligence (BI) and Big Data (BD) organisational culture. The study concludes that blockchain can transform supply chain management but acknowledges its limitations (Alnoukari, 2020).

Reverse logistics can prevent supply chain disruptions by reducing dependence on external suppliers and collaborating with third-party reverse logistics service providers. This requires collaboration and trust among supply chain partners. Various theories address supply chain phenomena, including the resource-based view, institutional theory, contingency theory, stakeholder theory, and dynamic capabilities theory (Paula et al., 2020). Technological disruptions like Blockchain, 3D printing, Artificial Intelligence, and the Internet of Things have also impacted supply chains. The Supply Chain Event Management (SCEM) model was validated by examining a real-world product distribution process with multiple agents (Bearzotti et al., 2008). Challenges such as lack of resources, awareness of sustainable tourism, and local authority support hinder responsible practices within South Africa.

The literature explores the impact of disruptive technologies on sustainable supply chains, identifying seven such technologies: blockchain, 3D printing, robotics, AI, cloud computing, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT) (Gamal et al., 2023). These technologies can enhance sustainability by reducing waste, improving resource management, and enhancing efficiency. Industry 4.0, characterised by six key technologies, is another aspect of disruptive technology that blends physical, digital, and biological realms (Mithas et al., 2022). Emerging technologies like 3D printing have the potential to revolutionise supply chain design and management, leading to mass customisation and manufacturing closer to markets (Waller, Fawcett, 2014). A study in Bahia Blanca, Argentina, examined a urea supply chain using a constraint satisfaction problem to instantiate a repair mechanism, outperforming manual methods automatically (Guarnaschelli et al., 2013). Also, investigating green bonds' hedging ability against global supply chain disruptions is crucial to maximising investment returns (Kong et al., 2023).

The Adaptive Dynamic Radio Open-Source Intelligent Team (ADROIT) framework outlines six components for understanding the potential value of these technologies: adding revenues,

differentiating products or services, reducing costs, optimising risks, innovating, and transforming business models and processes. The authors emphasise the need for more empirical studies on Industry 4.0 technologies, as current research focuses mainly on Operations Management and pre-Industry 4.0 technologies (Alfawaz, Alshehri, 2022)). The article also highlights the role of disruptive technology in sustainable development, emphasising the triple bottom-line approach and economic, social, and environmental aspects. The petroleum industry supply chain network is a prime example of how disruptive technology can enhance sustainability in various industries, noting that disruptive technology transcends industry and can be applied in different supply chains effectively and with sustainability (Kumar, Barua, 2022).

Disruptive innovation in agriculture, examining the concept and evaluating existing research. The review found that most research is qualitative and exploratory, focusing on food supply, technology adoption, digital risk management, and agriculture modernisation (Khan, Arif, 2023). Future research should focus on technology, system, and process innovation to disrupt the global agriculture value chain and replace traditional agriculture with new models. The study also highlights the potential of disruptive innovation to transform the agriculture sector and contribute to the global gross domestic product (Hendriksen, 2023). Education institutions should include Digital Innovation (DI) in agriculture curricula to improve agriculture education. The findings suggest that digital technologies positively impact supply chain resilience and robustness, with supply chain memory mediating (Yamamoto, 2022). The COVID-19 outbreak had a moderating effect on this relationship. Supply chain managers should focus on improving their supply chain memory to enhance their ability to recover from disruptions (Alvarenga et al., 2023).

The literature discusses adopting disruptive technologies like blockchain, 3D printing, AI, and IoT in supply chains, which align with SDG 9's focus on fostering innovation and technological advancements (Chauhan et al., 2022). These technologies can enhance sustainability, reduce waste, optimise resource management, and improve supply chain efficiency, contributing to building resilient infrastructure (Yamamoto, 2022). 3D printing's potential for mass customisation and manufacturing aligns with SDG 9's focus on supporting industry growth and adaptability. Supply chain resilience is also discussed, with the importance of memory in coping with disruptions, particularly in events like the COVID-19 outbreak (Sætra, 2021). Digital innovation in agriculture is also discussed, potentially disrupting the global value chain and replacing traditional agriculture with new models. In conclusion, the literature highlights the importance of disruptive technologies and innovation in supply chain management, which can positively impact building resilient infrastructure, promoting sustainable industrialisation, and fostering innovation. Incorporating Digital Innovation (DI) in agriculture curricula is crucial for achieving SDG 9's inclusive and sustainable industrialisation objectives (Shayan et al., 2022). Integration into the global value chain (GVC) has become a new driving force for economic growth in developing countries while simultaneously creating huge pressures for the reduction of carbon emissions (Wang et al., 2023).

This study explores the importance of partnerships, collaboration, and technology-driven innovations in addressing supply chain challenges and promoting sustainability. It highlights the role of blockchain technology in enhancing transparency, traceability, and accountability in supply chains, which can foster trust and collaboration among partners. Technological innovations like blockchain, 3D printing, AI, and the Internet of Things can transform supply chains through partnerships and collaboration, contributing to SDG 17's goal of fostering innovation (Ikram et al., 2018). The focus on supply chain resilience emphasises the importance of stakeholder partnerships to build resilient supply chains.

Disruptive technology can enhance sustainability in various industries, such as the petroleum industry, underscoring the potential for cross-sectoral partnerships (Friedman, Lewis, 2021). The study also highlights the need for partnerships between educational institutions, agricultural organisations, and technology providers in the agriculture sector to drive innovation and sustainability. Lastly, the study highlights the importance of supply chain memory and resilience, suggesting that supply chain managers must collaborate and share knowledge to enhance resilience (Chowdhury, Quaddus, 2017). This collaborative approach supports the idea of partnerships and information sharing, which are critical components of SDG 17. In conclusion, the literature highlights the relevance of partnerships, collaboration, and technology-driven innovations in addressing supply chain challenges and promoting

sustainability. These themes align with SDG 17's goal of encouraging partnerships for sustainable development (Genc, 2021).

The Triple Helix Model, developed by Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff in 1995, can be used to analyse the collaboration patterns, knowledge flow, and innovation dynamics in disruptive theory and supply chain management research in South Africa (Cai, Etzkowitz, 2020). The study focuses on academic institutions, industry, and government, analysing research output, influential authors, and themes. The government component should explore the impact of regulatory bodies, policies, and initiatives on the research landscape and encourage the application of disruptive theory in South African supply chain management practices (Zhou, Etzkowitz, 2021).

Globalisation has transformed the Triple Helix model, affecting the interplay between universities, industry, and government agencies. Addressing these challenges requires developing new conceptual tools or advancing existing ones, such as the Triple Helix model, to better understand innovation dynamics in the global economy (Smith, Leydesdorff, 2014). Policymakers can promote collaboration and knowledge exchange between sectors, creating incentives for innovation and entrepreneurship (Leydesdorff, 2005). In some cases, disruptive technologies in supply chain management may emerge due to collaboration within the Triple Helix model. For example, a university-government-industry partnership could lead to development an innovative AI-driven supply chain solution (Holmström, 2022).

Collaboration between these helices can influence supply chain innovation. For instance, government policies can shape logistics and trade regulations. At the same time, academia can contribute research and talent to improve supply chain technologies. In summary, disruption theory in supply chain management, the Triple Helix model, and the ADROIT framework are interconnected through their shared impact on innovation and technology adoption in supply chains (Smith, Leydesdorff, 2014). Collaboration among academia, government, and industry can drive the development and integration of disruptive AI technologies, ultimately shaping the future of supply chain management (ÓhÉigearthaigh et al., 2020).

3. Research methodology

The research approach is quantitative and qualitative, where the primary goal of this study is to evaluate sustainable supply chain and disruptive theory from a South African perspective. The researcher employed a bibliometric analysis. This type of analysis constitutes a systematic analytical technique that helps to determine the most influential scholars, their affiliations, and the keywords chosen (Fang et al., 2022). The bibliometric approach is appropriate when evaluating the current status of a particular discipline using different indicators such as highly cited publications, scholars, journals, academic institutions, and countries. Using bibliometrics, we can also assess research collaboration among scholars, institutions, and countries (Castillo, 2022). Therefore, this study draws on bibliometric analysis, a well-established form of meta-analytical research and a statistical method that identifies the qualitative and quantitative changes in a specific research topic as the ideal method to examine the current knowledge base on which disruptive theory and supply chain management research are interlinked (Gencer, Akkucuk, 2020).

4. Results

Data was taken from the Scopus database for the bibliometric analysis. Scopus, a top-tier scientific database with many articles, is renowned for its broad and trustworthy content (Elsevier B.V., 2020). The search string used was the following: ("disruptive" and "theory" and or" supply" and "Chain" and "Management"). The search was performed in the title, abstract and keywords fields. Only peer-reviewed journal articles in English were considered to ensure the literature's high quality and academic nature. The subject area was limited to business and management. Initially, the search query returned Sixty-seven documents. Sixty-seven documents were extracted in CSV format for the final analysis using the bibliometric tool VOSviewer version 1.6.19. This open-source computer program was developed to generate, visualise, and analyse term maps and a keyword co-occurrence network (Soeryanto Soegoto et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Publications in disruptive theory in SCM research

Table 1 analyses the affiliations of prominent academic institutions in research related to disruptive theory in SCM. The institutions are ranked based on their contributions to top journals.

Table 1. Affiliations in top academic institutions

Document Type	Number published
Article	71.6%
Conference paper	9%
Review	9%
Book Chapter	6%
Book	1.5%
Conference Review	1.5%
Editorial	1.5%

Figure 2 shows the most affiliations in top academic institutions of disruptive theory in SCM research as found in the Scopus database and ranked according to their output in top journals. The highest being University College London.

Figure 2. Affiliations in top academic institutions

Figure 3 shows that, out of the 67 publications on Scopus, 4852 references were used for the topic. The VOSviewer version used is (VOSviewer_1.6.19).

Figure 3. Publications

Figure 4 shows the phrases used in the 67 publications identified.

Figure 4. Publications phrases

5. Discussions

Figure 1 illustrates the trend of publications over the years. It highlights a significant increase in publications in 2022, where 14 out of 67 were recorded. This surge in 2022 represents 20.9% of the entire body of research related to disruptive theory in supply chain management (SCM). Table 1 illustrates the affiliations of prominent academic institutions in research on disruptive theory in SCM. The institutions are ranked based on their contributions to top journals, and it is revealed that University College London stands out as the leading contributor among them. Figure 2 shows a noteworthy finding.

Of the 67 publications examined in the study, 48 were identified as articles. These articles comprise 71.6% of the research on disruptive theory within SCM. This information is drawn from the comprehensive Scopus database. This finding underscores the diverse range of publication outlets chosen by researchers in this field. In summary, the text summarises critical observations and insights from these figures, outlining the significance of the data and trends presented in the visual representations of Scopus.

In figures 3 and 4, the network overlay reveals the number of authors cited or those who share a joint paper, encompassing 41 items distributed across 9 clusters connected by 87 links with a combined link strength totalling 132. Notably, Chide S.J. is associated with 4530 citations, Gunasekaran with 12293, and Gupta S. with 704 citations, all of which belong to cluster 1, representing the cluster with the highest number of authors. Within the VOS Viewer, among 4123 authors, a group of 75 authors successfully surpasses the established threshold criteria. Specifically, these authors have authored at least five documents and garnered at least five citations, reflecting their significant contributions and impact within the dataset. Using the bibliometric tool VOS Viewer, we can observe that the average publication year varies across different terms within the dataset. For instance, the term "Research" appears 89 times, with an average publication year of 2009.24, and is associated with Cluster 4, which contains 24 links. Similarly, the word "Disruptive innovation" occurs ten times with an average publication year of 2012.20 and is also linked to Cluster 4, which has connections to research-related topics.

In contrast, "Supply Chain Risk Management" appears 15 times with an average publication year of 2011.47, residing in Cluster 3 and connected to 9 distinct links related to various aspects such as firm performance, review, research, role, effect, empirical investigation, antecedent, and relationship. Lastly, "Blockchain" is mentioned 115 times with an average publication year of 2018.70, linked to Cluster 6 and associated with 26 links. The dataset comprises 92 terms, of which 55 have been selected, constituting 60% of the dataset. There are 55 items distributed across 7 clusters, interconnected by 344 links, with a cumulative link strength of 750. The bibliometric tool represents country-specific citation data visually. Among the 124 countries included in the analysis, a notable cohort of 42 countries has successfully met the predefined threshold criteria, which necessitates each country to have produced a minimum of 5 documents and accrued at least five citations. For instance, South Africa emerges with nine papers, positioned within Cluster 1, boasting an average publication year 2014.22. Furthermore, it exhibits a network of 20 links with a cumulative link strength of 103, underscoring its research prominence. In contrast, the USA stands out with a substantial 751 documents located within Cluster 1, reflecting an average publication year 2009.10. It maintains a comprehensive network of 41 links, demonstrating an impressive link strength of 7975, emphasising its substantial research influence. Lastly, Chile contributes six documents and finds its place in Cluster 4, with an average publication year 2010.17. It establishes connections through 14 links, collectively exhibiting a link strength of 62, illustrating its scholarly contributions and collaborative ties within the dataset.

6. Conclusions

This paper presents a comprehensive overview of research on disruptive theory in supply chain management (SCM). It provides insights into publication trends, academic affiliations, and research articles, highlighting the growing prominence of disruptive theory in SCM research (Singh et al., 2021). The dataset also includes bibliometrics, revealing collaborative patterns among authors and the impact of their citations. Notable authors like Chide S.J., Gunasekaran, and Gupta S. are highlighted, while 75 authors meet stringent criteria for document output and citations.

The dataset's richness is evident as it spans a wide range of terms and clusters, showcasing the multifaceted nature of disruptive theory in SCM research (Yu, Hang, 2010). The analysis of country-specific citation data in Figure 5 highlights the global research reach in this field, with 42 countries meeting predefined document and citation threshold criteria. South Africa, the USA, and Chile exemplify distinct research profiles within the dataset. The findings enrich our understanding of disruptive theory in SCM research, its global impact, and the dynamic nature of scholarly contributions (Weilbach et al., 2023). These insights are valuable for researchers, academicians, and practitioners seeking to contribute to this evolving domain.

Research gaps exist in understanding how disruptive theory can drive eco-friendly practices, circular economy principles, and sustainable sourcing in the South African supply chain (Khan, Arif, 2023). Research could focus on understanding the challenges and opportunities for SMEs or big businesses in South Africa to adopt and benefit from disruptive innovations, potentially leading to more inclusive growth and development (Rojas-Berrio et al., 2022).

The literature has identified research gaps by authors, presented as follows. Localised Application of Disruptive Theory: While disruptive theory has been extensively studied in global supply chain contexts, there needs to be a research gap in understanding how disruptive theory applies explicitly to the unique challenges and dynamics of the South African supply chain (Flavin, 2021). Integration of Technology and Innovation: Disruptive technologies, such as blockchain, Internet of Things (IoT), and artificial intelligence, can potentially revolutionise supply chains (Tortorella et al., 2021). However, there is a need for research that focuses on how these technologies can be effectively integrated within the South African supply chain context, considering factors like infrastructure limitations, digital divide, and technological readiness (Gemici, Alpkhan, 2015).

The literature review provides practical examples of how disruptive technologies have impacted supply chains in various industries, from petroleum to tourism. This information is valuable for businesses across different sectors looking to adapt to technological changes effectively (Rojas-Berrio et al., 2022). It also highlights how innovation can positively impact countries like South Africa, leading to sustainable economic growth and competitive advantage. This insight is essential for SA governments, education, and businesses looking to stimulate economic development through technological advancements (Qureshil et al., 2009). The study recognises challenges South African businesses might face in their supply chain ecosystem. It seeks to address innovations to enhance supply chain resilience and the potential to transform the agriculture sector and contribute to global Gross Domestic Product by including government regulation, digital inclusion in curricula and equipping businesses with knowledge and collaborators to improve supply chain strategies (Zuiderwijk et al., 2021).

Policymakers must adapt regulations and policies to support the effective integration of disruptive technologies in South Africa. Skill development and human capital development are crucial for supply chain professionals to stay relevant and harness the full potential of disruption (Hendriksen, 2023)). Understanding future trends in disruptive theory and supply chain management in South Africa is critical for organisations to position themselves for success in an increasingly disruptive and technologically driven business environment (Kumar, Barua, 2022).

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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